

CONSTRUCTION AND VALIDATION OF INSTITUTIONAL CLIMATE SCALE (ICS) FOR B.ED. TEACHER-TRAINEES

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ABSTRACT

Present research task is a process of standardization of self made research tool name "**Institutional Climate Scale (ICS)**" to analyze the facilities of B.Ed. College. Total 4 dimensions were identified and 95 statements were drafted for pre tryout and after the clearance of ten educational experts 64 items were finalized in which, 36 items were favourable and 28 items were unfavourable. Against each item there are five responses as strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and strongly Disagree. For the purpose of tryout, the drafted scale was administrated among 200 B.Ed. teacher-trainees of 4 B.Ed. Colleges (2 Aided B.Ed. Colleges and 2 Private B.Ed. Colleges) of district Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh. After item analysis, 45 items were selected to finalize the **Institutional Climate Scale (ICS)**. The reliability of developed Institutional Climate Scale was 0.9205 with Spearman Brown Prophecy formula. The validity of tool was also satisfactory according educational experts.

Keywords : Construction, Institutional Climate Scale (ICS), B.Ed. teacher- trainees.

Introduction :

Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, beliefs and habits (Dewey, 1944). Education plays a vital role in the development of human and is linked with an individual's well being and opportunities for better living (Battle & Lewis, 2002).

Formal education provides school, college and educational institution etc. If the climate of school, college and educational institution improve, then the students studying in school, college and educational institution will not only become high academic achievers but will also become excellent professional. Good educational institution climate will make efficient, job oriented, mentally healthy and skillful higher citizens.

Institutional Climate

Generally, the climate of the institution reflects the atmosphere of the institution. The climate of institution refers to the basic requirements like

infrastructure/physical facilities, administration, managerial behavior and resources etc. Positive, supportive, democratic and authentic climate of the institution create the success of the institution. Attractive, conducive climate in an institution leads to motivation which brings job satisfaction to the employees of the institution.

Institutional Climate for B.Ed. Course

The climate of B.Ed. institution refers the current status, position and situation of the institution, infrastructure/physical climate, academic climate, social climate, administrative climate & resources etc. which help in the development of knowledge, understanding, ability to analyze, synthesize and evaluate skills (Physical and mental) as well as develop desirable value and attitude among B.Ed. students.

To measures the institution climate of B.Ed. teacher-trainees the researcher studied many tools such as Organizational Climate Scale developed by Vinita

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Singh, College Climate Questionnaire developed by **A.K. Gaur**, School Climate Scale developed by **S. P. Singh & A. Imam**, Classroom Climate Scale developed by **P. Shrinivasan & K. Suresh**, Academic Climate Description Questionnaire developed by **M. L. Shah & Amita Shah**, School Environment Inventory developed by **K. S. Mishra**, School Environment Scale developed by **Shweta Agarwal & Shalini Pandey** and Student's Institution Satisfaction Scale developed by **S. Ali & S. K. Jha**. After critical review of relevant various scale but no suitable standardized tool was found to assess the institutional climate for B.Ed. teacher-trainees. Hence, the researcher decided to develop the institution climate

scale (ICS) for B.Ed. teacher-trainees by herself with the help of her supervisor^v

Construction of the Institutional Climate Scale (ICS)

The process of construction of institutional climate scale for B.Ed. was carried out in three phases

- I. Planning Phase
- II. Construction Phase
- III. Standardization Phase.

(1) Pre Draft of Institutional Climate Scale

To assess the institutional climate scale for B.Ed. teacher-trainees following four dimensions of institutional climate were selected for inclusion in the present scale.

Dimensions :-

Physical Climate	Building, Furniture, Library, toilet facility, availability of clean drinking water.
Academic Climate	Qualified and trained teacher, co -curricular activities, Guidance and Counseling for students and classes are running regularly according to time-table.
Social Climate	Teacher and student maintain good cooperation, Teacher maintain mutual respect, A healthy relationship exists among principal, teachers and students.
Administrative Climate	Presence of grievance redressed cell, office staff, supporting staff and technical assistant.

Preparation, Collection & Editing of Statements for Pre Draft of Scale

The researcher prepared the pre draft of institutional climate scale comprising of 95 statements. The statements were developed both in Hindi & English language.

Items were framed on the basis of information available journal, articles, books, newspapers, official sources, web sources, NCTE Gazette 2014 for B.Ed., NCFTE 2009 to literature related to institutional climate were taken into account, while framing statements for the scale. For the pre draft, 95 items were tentatively framed in the form of statements and a five point rating scale was developed for each item.

Pre Tryout and Evaluation

The pre draft of 95 items was shown to various experts to examine the content, repetitiveness and ambiguity of the items. The researcher along with her supervisor devoted several sitting to consider the judgments of the experts on the statements relating to institutional climate. The items were thoroughly screened and edited. The items which were overlapping were carefully examined. Some items were modified and some of them were dropped. After making these changes, 64 items were shortlisted from 95 items.

(2) Second Draft of Institutional Climate Scale

Second draft of institutional climate scale consisted of 64 items, in which 36 statements were

favourable and 28 statements were unfavourable. The distribution of selected items of the second draft institutional climate scale is given in the table-1

Table-1: Distribution of selected statement of the second draft institutional climate scale.

Dimensions	Favourable items	Unfavourable Items	No. of Favourable items	No. of Unfavourable items	Total
Physical Climate	1,3,4,18, 20,34,36, 51,52,53, 55,57	2,5,19,21,33, 37, 38	12	7	19
Academic Climate	8,11,24, 25,26,40, 41,42,43, 47,60,61	6,7,9,10,22, 44, 58,59,62	12	9	21
Social Climate	12,27,29,30, 46,48,54	13,14,28,45, 63	7	5	12
Administrative Climate	31, 39, 50, 56, 64	15,16,17,23,32, 35,49	5	7	12
Total			36	28	64

Second Tryout & Evaluation of the Second Draft Institutional Climate Scale (ICS)

For the purpose of the try out, the draft scale was administered to 200 B.Ed. teacher trainees of 4 B.Ed. College (2 Aided B.Ed. College and 2 Private B.Ed. College) of Bareilly district. The B.Ed. Colleges for tryout were selected by using purposive sampling and 50 B.Ed. teacher-trainees of the every selected B.Ed. college were included in the sample. Necessary instructions were prepared and included in the beginning of the draft Institutional Climate Scale. Oral instructions were also provided whenever necessary. The time limit fixed for the completion of the responses was 30 minutes. The scoring

procedure described earlier was followed in tryout of the draft Institutional Climate Scale.

Item Analysis

The respond draft Institutional Climate Scale (ICS) of 200 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was scored by using the scoring process as mentioned earlier and then arranged in an order from the highest score to the lowest score. Then 27% (i.e.-54) of the B.Ed. teacher-trainees from the top and 27% (i.e. 54) of the B.Ed. teacher-trainees from the bottom were taken apart. Thus two groups, viz. high and low scoring groups were formed. The mean and standard deviation for each individual item by high scoring group and low scoring group were computed.

Table 2:- t-ratio in respect of 64 items for institutional climate scale (ICS)

Item No.	t-Ratio	Result	Item No.	t-Ratio	Result
1.	6.58	Significant	33.	6.22	Significant
2.	1.93	N.S.	34.	5.66	Significant
3.	1.95	N.S.	35.	2.29	N.S.

4.	1.82	N.S.	36.	7.22	Significant
5.	6.19	Significant	37.	4.97	Significant
6.	5.23	Significant	38.	7.39	Significant
7.	2.12	N.S.	39.	6.82	Significant
8.	7.57	Significant	40.	7.42	Significant
9.	5.83	Significant	41.	6.31	Significant
10.	1.83	N.S.	42.	6.52	Significant
11.	1.91	N.S.	43.	1.95	N.S.
12.	5.57	Significant	44.	5.96	Significant
13.	4.76	Significant	45.	0.28	N.S.
14.	4.81	Significant	46.	2.43	N.S.
15.	5.02	Significant	47.	6.59	Significant
16.	6.98	Significant	48.	6.64	Significant
17.	7.82	Significant	49.	1.83	N.S.
18.	5.13	Significant	50.	5.0	Significant
19.	4.79	Significant	51.	2.38	N.S.
20.	7.56	Significant	52.	1.17	N.S.
21.	5.92	Significant	53.	6.53	Significant
22.	6.80	Significant	54.	8.51	Significant
23.	6.13	Significant	55.	5.61	Significant
24.	8.77	Significant	56.	7.08	Significant
25.	7.43	Significant	57.	6.46	Significant
26.	8.21	Significant	58.	2.13	N.S.
27.	7.63	Significant	59.	0.89	N.S.
28.	2.11	N.S.	60.	6.44	Significant
29.	1.94	N.S.	61.	2.23	N.S.
30.	1.79	N.S.	62.	6.32	Significant
31.	5.38	Significant	63.	4.83	Significant
32.	6.46	Significant	64.	6.79	Significant

In the present case, the t-value of the 45 items was more than 2.58. After computing the t-value of item and selecting the statements for final draft of the scale.

(3) Final Draft of Institutional Climate Scale

The final draft of the institutional climate scale by arranged the selecting 45 items in random manner in a

single format. The distribution of the favourable & unfavourable statements were carried out in four dimensions of institutional climate, which is provided in table-3.

Table -3

Dimensions	Favourable items	Unfavourable Items	No. of Favourable items	No. of Unfavourable items	Total
Physical Climate	1,7,9,25,27,41,44	2,16,20,30,32	7	5	12
Academic Climate	3,11,13,15, 31,34	4,6,22,39,43	6	5	11
Social Climate	5,17,19,23, 36,40	8,10,26,33,37	6	5	11
Administrative Climate	21,29,38,42, 45	12,14,18,24, 28,35	5	6	11
Total			24	21	45

Scoring Procedure

There are 45 statements in the scale, 24 statements of the scale were favourable and 21 statements were unfavourable. The scale is self administering and self reporting five point scale. Against each item, there are five response Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A) Undecided(U), Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree

(SD). The response with which the subject agrees is to be ticked by the subject. Scoring for favourable statements, award 5 mark on strongly agree, 4 mark on agree, 3 mark on undecided, 2 mark on disagree and 1 mark on strongly disagree. For unfavourable statements scoring procedure is completely reversed. The scoring key were determined as given in the table-4

Table -4 : Scoring key for the Responses

Nature of Items	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (DA)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
Favourable	5	4	3	2	1
Unfavourable	1	2	3	4	5

III. Standardization Phase

Reliability of Institutional Climate Scale (ICS)

Split Half Reliability method was used for

calculating the reliability of the developed tool Institutional Climate Scale (ICS). The score obtained was divided into two equal halves. Odd-even method was

used to split the test into two halves. Then, the coefficient of correlation between those parts of the test was calculated using the formula of product moment coefficient. It was found to be **0.852**. The coefficient of reliability of the whole test was then estimated by using spearman-Brown Prophecy formula and the reliability of the full test was found to be **0.9205**. It shows that the developed tool of Institutional Climate Scale (ICS) was a reliable tool.

Validity of the Institutional Climate Scale (ICS)

The scale has high content validity since all the items have been included in the scale only after seeking the opinion and approvals of the educational experts. Besides these items of the scale were selected after carefully scrutinizing the definition of institutional climate and its dimensions, hence scale has fair degree of content validity.

Conclusion

The reliability of the scale was found as **0.9205** which is a satisfactory one for such quantitative research. Thus, the Institutional Climate Scale (ICS) has been prepared for the final administration.

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